

Supplementary File 5: Cardiorespiratory Results

Data Screening and Diagnostics

Data screening indicated no univariate outliers. The normality assumption was not met for both heart rate ($p < .001$) and respiration rate ($p = .011$). An ordered quantile normalization transformation (Peterson & Cavanaugh, 2020) was applied to remedy this.

Heart and Respiratory Rates

The oneway RM ANOVA on heart rate showed no significant main effect of condition, $F(1.52, 44.09) = 1.60, p = .216, \eta_p^2 = .05$. The oneway RM ANOVA on respiratory rate showed a significant main effect of condition, $F(2, 70) = 6.47, p = .003, \eta_p^2 = .16$; nonetheless, the post hoc tests did not reach significance ($M_{\text{music}} = 0.71, SD_{\text{music}} = 0.16; M_{\text{audiobook}} = 0.69, SD_{\text{audiobook}} = 0.11; M_{\text{control}} = 0.65, SD_{\text{control}} = 0.12$). Overall, the results indicated that heart and respiratory rates were not influenced by condition (see Figure 1).

Figure 1

Heart Rate and Respiratory Rate

Note. Box plots and probability density functions or mean points and 95% confidence intervals are displayed for each condition. Each dot represents an individual participant.

References

Peterson, R. A., & Cavanaugh, J. E. (2020). Ordered quantile normalization: A semiparametric transformation built for the cross-validation era. *Journal of Applied Statistics*, 47(13–15) 2312–2327. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02664763.2019.1630372>